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VISUAL MUSIC IN THE PLANETARIUMS OF LATIN AMERICAN AND THE CARIBBEAN REGION

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“Broken Space” visual music composition by Alejandro Casales at “Efemera” full-dome festival, 2024. Planetarium of the Federal University of Santa Catarina, Brazil. Photo: Jefferson Ferreira, used with permission.

ABSTRACT

The planetariums in the Latin American and the Caribbean region have a story to tell. Initially, the region consists of 35 countries with enormous geographical diversity, surface heterogeneity, and variety in population and socioeconomic characteristics; it has a rich cultural variety and different degrees of development (Ortíz et al. 2003).

In this context, the construction of planetariums began in 1955 in Uruguay; subsequently, they spread to Brazil, Mexico, Peru, Venezuela, Cuba, Argentina, and Colombia. Since then, new planetariums have been built in the region.

The main focus of planetariums is astronomical education, but they also present shows in the arts and humanities. Among the shows are visual music concerts, with the goal of attracting new audiences to get to know the planetarium and encouraging them to attend its educational activities.

However, visual music presentations have not always shared the same objectives, due to the variety of interests that each planetarium may have. This article presents the origin of visual music and its development in Latin America and the Caribbean.

INTRODUCTION

The function of planetariums is to serve as venues for the exploration of astronomy while simultaneously acting as educational environments where hemispherical projections are displayed on a half-dome screen. Within these facilities, it is possible to present natural phenomena and astronomical narratives that encompass a wide range of content (Sumners et al. 2008). Inside these immersive spaces, visitors can engage in interactive experiences, participate in guided tours, and attend lectures that deepen their understanding of celestial events and the universe at large. By combining visual storytelling with scientific inquiry, planetariums foster a sense of wonder and curiosity about the cosmos. This capability has prompted the establishment of planetariums globally, thereby attracting audiences of all age groups.

Since the 1950 decade, planetariums in the Latin American and the Caribbean region have flourished, propelled by technological advancements in star projectors developed in the United States, Europe, and Asia. This progress was facilitated by notable inventions such as the Atwood sphere and projectors from esteemed companies including Zeiss, Spitz, GOTO, Minolta, and StarLab, among others.

The first planetarium was established in 1955 in Montevideo, Uruguay, subsequently followed by another in São Paulo, Brazil, in 1957; then one in Mexico City in 1959; followed by the planetarium of Lima City in Peru in 1960; Caracas City in Venezuela in 1961; Havana City in Cuba in 1964; Buenos Aires City in Argentina and Bogotá City in Colombia, both in 1967. Later, new planetariums expanded to additional cities throughout the region.

Educationally, planetariums have endeavored to align with local science curriculum objectives in educational institutes through astronomical projections and geophysical data. Some

(From top) Planetarium of Montevideo City in Uruguay; Planetarium of São Paulo City in Brazil; Planetarium of Lima City in Peru. All images: CC BY-SA 4.0

planetariums operate educational programs that adhere to universal standards of science education. These programs encompass informal teaching activities emphasizing comprehension of scientific research as well as providing educational resources tailored for various age groups and teachers.

While the primary focus of planetariums is on astronomical education, they also host performances related to the arts and humanities. These include visual music concerts, poetry readings under the stars, theatrical presentations, laser

light shows, scientific lectures, academic discussions, and special events; such activities constitute an essential aspect of the experience within a planetarium theater and are often conducted on a regular basis.

Among their shows, you can find visual music concerts, which aim to attract new audiences to get to know the planetarium and encourage them to attend its educational activities. However, visual music presentations in Latin America and the Caribbean region have not always shared the same objectives, due to the variety of interests that each planetarium may have. The following section explores the origin of visual music and its recent development in Latin America and the Caribbean.

VISUAL MUSIC IN PLANETARIUMS

A review of the historical development of planetariums reveals that, at the beginning of the last century, innovative forms of visual music emerged in the United States. This concept encompasses artistic visual creations that are projected with musical accompaniment. The initial manifestations were paintings that did not necessitate sound but implied it as an essential component for structuring their content. Subsequently, advancements in technology introduced various methods and devices to visually depict sound or its musical characteristics through imagery (Payling, 2023). This particular mode of creation facilitated collaboration among artists from diverse disciplines such as art, music, dance, and literature. It also gave shape to new artistic styles like kinetic art, op art, psychedelia, concrete music, experimentalism, jazz, and modern dance.

From 1957 to 1959, a collective of creators enhanced the functionalities of the planetarium theater by presenting a series of concerts titled “Vortex: Experiments in Light and Sound.” These events were orchestrated by sound artist Henry Jacobs and filmmaker Jordan Belson and took place at the Morrison Planetarium within the California Academy of Sciences in the United States. They attracted substantial audiences and were conceived as an immersive artistic experience—a novel form of theater founded on the synthesis of electronics, optics, and music aimed directly at engaging the senses (Center for Visual Music, 2023).

In their operations, the immersive features of the planetarium theater gained a performative aspect through multimedia configurations that employed various projection methods, multichannel audio systems, kinetic elements, interactive components, and improvisational techniques (Keefer, 2008).

For its realization, Henry Jacobs and Jordan Belson, used the works of other artists who were influential in their areas, such as Bruno Maderna, David L. Talcott, Gordon Longfellow, Gyorgy Ligeti, George Abend, Hy Hirsh, James Whitney, James Cunningham, Jim Fassett, Jose Duarte, Karlheinz Stockhausen, Luciano Berio, LK Dunham, Luc

Ferrari, Moon B. Raymakers, Oskar Fischinger, Pieter Van Deusen, Russ García, Toshiro Mayuzumi, Toru Takemitsu, Vladimir Ussachevsky, William Loughborough, among others (Adi Newton, 2023).

The “Vortex” concerts occurred during a period marked by significant technological advancements. The predominant star projectors utilized in planetariums were primarily derived from German innovations, providing immersive experiences designed to visualize astronomical data from outer space. But the Morrison Planetarium developed its own optomechanical projector, facilitating a platform for experimentation. Henry Jacobs and Jordan Belson harnessed this technology as a temporal medium, enabling the integration of the musical dimension. Consequently, they showcased visual music compositions utilizing specialized devices within the optomechanical projector that projected intricate interference patterns. Furthermore, their setup included 30 slide projectors, kaleidoscopes, strobe lights, and Moiré pattern projectors; this unique combination produced unprecedented light and sound environments (California Academy of Sciences, 2023).

On the other hand, their audio technology was distinguished by a surround sound system comprising 38 speakers strategically arranged in a circular configuration within the planetarium theater, complemented by a mechanism that allowed for their rotation around the circumference. They opted for magnetic tape due to its efficacy as a medium for content reproduction in their era.

Henry Jacobs and Jordan Belson conducted approximately one hundred concerts. Unfortunately, in 1959, the Morrison Planetarium withdrew its support, without fully realizing its potential (Ibid.).

However, the “Vortex” concerts significantly enhanced the potential of planetariums and their scientific outreach initiatives, leading to the adaptation of their technologies for deployment across various countries and within diverse cultural contexts.

In contemporary discourse, the forms of visual music that emerged during the “Vortex” era continue to hold significant relevance, particularly through the advancements in digital technology, which facilitate the seamless integration of sound and imagery in digital formats. Furthermore, the methodologies for visual production have been widely adopted, alongside techniques for musicalization and

“Hatun Mayo” a multidisciplinary concert by Carlos Trujillo and Katia Hinojosa, organized to celebrate 100 years of planetariums around the world. Concert held in Cusco planetarium in Peru, 2024. <https://planetariumcusco.com/hatunmayu/>
Photo: Planetarium Cusco, used with permission.

sound dissemination. This evolution can be attributed to the normalization and standardization of production technologies, enabling creators and researchers from diverse regions to incorporate the foundational principles of visual music into their work across global stages.

Today, an examination of visual music reveals a rich array of methods, techniques, and theoretical discussions aimed at refining its definition. Terms such as videomusic and audiovisual are often used to describe its form and creation within analogous contexts.

The term videomusic involves electronic music, acoustic music, and computational media combined with images. The term audiovisual is defined as the combination of sound and image in a single work. In all terms, the relationships between sound and image are deliberated to cohere (Paying, 2023).

In this context, the innovative expressions of visual music have intermittently been incorporated into programs aimed at scientific outreach and the advancement of astronomy and space sciences across various Latin American and the Caribbean nations. This integration seeks to enhance their mission of fostering societal knowledge and promoting universal culture.

For example, in the last four years, Argentina and its planetarium in Buenos Aires have occasionally held visual music concerts called “Understanding Visual Music.” Brazil and the planetariums in the cities of Brasilia and Salvador de Bahia host the “Immersphere” festival, while the planetarium of the Federal University of Santa Catarina hosts the “Efemera” festival. In Colombia, the planetariums in the cities of Bogota and Medellin host the “Domo Lleno” festival. In Costa Rica, the planetarium of the University of Costa Rica occasionally holds experimental music concerts and shows such as “Drift.” In Chile, the planetarium of the University of Santiago hosts the “Küze” festival. In Mexico, the Papalote immersive dome in Mexico City and the Pendulo planetarium in Queretaro City host

the “Dome Arte” festival; the Cuernavaca City immersive dome occasionally hosts its visual music show, and the planetariums in Cozumel, Cancun, and Playa del Carmen host visual music concerts. In Peru, the Morro Solar planetarium in Lima City occasionally hosts the “Visions Art” festival, and the Cusco planetarium recently hosted the “Hatun Mayu” choral concert. In Venezuela, the Humboldt planetarium in Caracas City occasionally hosts “Concerts for the Universe.” In Uruguay, the Montevideo planetarium hosts concerts by the Montevideo Philharmonic Orchestra and festivals with artistic events, among other activities.

In the integration of visual music forms within Latin American and Caribbean nations, three axes can be discerned that facilitate the analysis of their adaptation: appropriation of standardized technologies within diverse cultural contexts, presentation of artistic works without limitations on their narratives, and co-creation of extended virtual spaces and shared immersive experiences. Each axis will be explained in the following part.

APPROPRIATION OF STANDARDIZED TECHNOLOGIES WITHIN DIVERSE CULTURAL CONTEXTS

The visual music programs implemented in Latin America and the Caribbean are distinguished by their utilization of standardized technology. This encompasses a comprehensive array of devices designed for the operation of planetariums, which adhere to established specifications to ensure interoperability and compatibility across diverse technological contexts, often lacking direct ties to local cultural elements.

In essence, these technologies are adopted largely due to the influence of scientific methodologies that can be replicated through standardized technological instruments. This includes astronomical performance spaces equipped with spherical screens, projection systems, lighting and laser setups, sound and microphone arrangements, as well as software frameworks facilitating the operation of each system. Additionally, there are logical supports for creating virtual environments and projecting specialized astronomical data, along with those enabling sound creation and musical accompaniment for projections.

One notable advantage of technological standardization is the capacity to visualize three-dimensional data derived from two-dimensional graphical representations. This transformation constitutes a conceptual process that proves beneficial not only for the art of “astrovisualization” but also extends its utility to other disciplines or artistic expressions such as visual music.

In astronomical studies, the astrovisualization of data enables a detailed examination of the size and scale of the universe, as well as celestial bodies. These processes are carried out with techniques and capabilities that were not previously available. Therefore, technological standardization allows for liberation from the mechanical forms of the past (Emmart, 2005).

Currently, scientists and artists from Latin America and the Caribbean have managed to develop their own three-dimensional materials, providing them the possibility to create their own 3D environments and graphic elements with realistic appearances from all sides and angles. This allows them to develop their creative capacities for three-dimensional visualization and auditory perception in order to create intense immersive experiences in their planetariums.

PRESENTATION OF ARTISTIC WORKS WITHOUT LIMITATIONS IN THEIR NARRATIVES

When the audience appreciates visual music works, there is no predominant orientation regarding what can be perceived in a dome. Nevertheless, there is an overwhelming notion concerning the proper orientation within a 180° stage, whether due to the inclination of its screen, its scale, the position of the viewer and the audience, and, of course, the immersive quality of the work being observed.

At this point, creative freedom becomes a surprise for the audience, as they will not be experiencing astronomical or geoscientific information. Therefore, the information received will relate to the subjectivity of the artist and their creative processes.

On one hand, viewers tend to associate visual music works with information from television screens and cinematography, where visual processes are more connected to commercial culture, turning the immersive experiences of planetarium theaters into challenging moments that can be seen as experimental since there is no preconceived idea of what will be observed.

Inclusively, visual music works can be categorized into two forms: the first, 360° films with limited duration that feature no interactivity with the spectators, and the second, real-time performances accompanied by musicians, dancers, or actors.

On the other hand, many programs dedicated to visual music in Latin America and the Caribbean do not undergo the same process as astronomical or geoscientific programs, where there is scientific rigor in their production and data integration within a dome.

That is, the artistic works and the technological requirements for high-quality scientific visualizations are very different. In a way, artistic works take advantage of technological advancements to present their ideas, which aim to be available in a dome, while scientific visualizations can take decades to mature their information to suit the technological characteristics of a specific projection system before finally being displayed in a planetarium.

CO-CREATION OF EXTENDED VIRTUAL SPACES AND SHARED IMMERSIVE EXPERIENCES

Current forms of creation in art involve combined experiences and the use of extended spaces, both real and virtual, online and offline. In them, co-creation provides a form of collective artistic creation, which allows for

(Continued on pg. 57)

Music (con't.)

the evaluation of goals and strategies to preserve artistic quality and its distribution. Likewise, it allows immersive experiences to reach audiences from different countries and contexts, achieving regional connectivity in closed circuits that are sustained by the synergy within a technosphere. That is, the transformation of the physical environment through the technological connectivity of the network and its convergence in shared virtual spaces.

In other words, it is the co-creation of new worlds through three-dimensionally modeled environments that will be projected onto various domes of planetariums. The new worlds can be conceptually simple, up to sharing complex systems of measurement and astronomical information and geophysical accuracy that can aid regional development, beyond the dissemination of knowledge.

CONCLUSIONS

The “Vortex” concerts by Henry Jacobs and Jordan Belson were fundamental in conceiving the planetarium as a pulsating space for artistic expression through light and sound, impacting the way they attracted new audiences of their time. Likewise, they expanded the conventional forms of artistic production and presentation in 360°, innovating through the use of technological devices that had not been employed before, transforming the modes of visual and auditory reception.

Jordan Belson at one point stated that the “Vortex” concerts did not aim to overwhelm the viewer but rather to create audiovisual experiences that transcend traditional cinema by eliminating the boundaries of the screen and the division between the audience and the projection. Thus, the entire domed space of the planetarium became a living theater (Center for Visual Music, 2023).

However, the current presentation of visual music works in planetariums across Latin America and the Caribbean is limited to occasional performances, so it remains necessary to better understand the archetypal, architectural, and perceptual characteristics of each planetarium. Additionally, it is important to consider the sociocultural relationships and transformations in each context, including the pedagogical ones.

On one hand, the significance of presenting and experiencing visual music works combined with educational activities in planetariums in the Latin America and the Caribbean region is based on their effectiveness for the benefit of learning and the development of its inhabitants. This can be utilized to reflect on the issues that connect human beings with their physical environment and contribute to the transformation of Latin America and the Caribbean, a region marked by social imbalances and the dehumanization of millions of people (United Nations Development Programme, 2023)

In this sense, dehumanization is understood as a series of violations against citizens; it is the annulment of

human rights for men and women aimed at controlling their development by limiting their social, cognitive, and economic capacities.

According to the 2020 Human Development Report (Ibid.), technological innovation processes must contribute to thinking about and remedying the damages to reverse them in favor of the planet and human values. Therefore, actions are necessary to enhance the practical and intellectual capacities of men and women, especially through activities that enable them to act in favor of their freedom.

Finally, the creation and dissemination of visual music artworks, along with their combination with educational activities, could enhance their effectiveness in dehumanized communities with limited access to artistic experiences. From that point on, it could be discovered that the immersive art of visual music serves as a form of expression that transforms perceptions of the environment and provokes unusual responses that stimulate imagination and desires for freedom.

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Translations

Translations can be found on the IPS Website:

https://ips-planetarium.site-ym.com/resource/resmgr/pdf-articles/casales_portuguese.docx.pdf

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